

An Investigation Of Training And Development Towards Employee Performance: An Empirical Approach From Nurses

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 11 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 14, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Employee Performance, Feedback, Learning retention, Opportunity to use, Trained nurses</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5571012</p>	<p><i>The present study attempts to investigate employee performance (EP) among the nurses of Balochistan, Pakistan. The analysis is quantitative and applies a survey questionnaire to collect the cross-sectional data. A random sampling technique is applied for targeting the study units. At first, we distributed 450 surveys personally among the different government hospitals in Balochistan. In return, we got 306 valid samples. It yields a 68% response rate. Finally, the study utilizes 306 usable answers to conclude the final consequences. By employing the SEM, the outcomes show a positive significant influence of feedback, learning retention (LR) and opportunity to use (OTU) on EP. The research outcomes would offer guidelines for top management and government agent for enhancing the EP in different contexts. The study would encourage the government to focus on training and development as it has a significant role in improving the EP. Finally, the findings of the study would enrich the literature on management and HRM.</i></p>

Introduction

In the present era, the EP has great importance in enhancing the profit of the organization. Therefore, developing skills and knowledge through training programs is the need of the day (Bhatti et al., 2021a). Several scholars have shown a moderately attentive role of the work environment in outlining the construct of transfer (Pugh & Bergin, 2006; Blume et al., 2010). With significant investments, organizations remain hesitant about the magnitude to which employees perform contrarily once back on the job (Blume et al., 2010). Employees are considered the family and asset of modern organizations (i.e., financial assets) that make the skills to overcome the future challenges of an organization. The best employee performance well to do a successful business (Cheng & Hampson, 2008; Brown & McCracken, 2009). According to Jalloh and Jalloh (2016), the employees make their organization fruitful with the best performance. They are also considered the backbone for the prosperity of their organizations (Sriviboon & Jermstiparsert, 2019). Riley et al. (2017), Kerdpitak and Jermstiparsert (2019) demonstrate that individuals' training results from robust investments in human capital. It enhances the skills of the employee through training. Similarly, Iqbal and Dastgeer (2017) suggest that training develops efficiency among employees, leading to enhancing organizations' performance. However, some scholars like Teck-Hua and Catherine (2015) and Alwekasi (2015) believe in the dependence of practical training on the practical training approaches in the learning process. An empirical investigation of Burke and Hutchins (2007) emphasized a significant and positive role of supervisory support, LR, feedback and OTU in performance. Feedback has a robust share in enhancing the performance of the firms. It signifies a signal from management to individuals of how they are performing and near the performance (Holton et al., 2000). Effectiveness in training is possible through sturdy support, peers and subordinates, and top management (Baldwin & Ford, 1988). Finally, OTU improves the organization's performance through motivation and knowledge transfer (Yamhill & McLean, 2001; Chen et al., 2007). Taking into account the significance of training and development in enhancing the EP, the current investigation efforts to look at the role of feedback, LR and OTU towards EP among the nurses of Pakistan. The study's outcomes would provide sufficient guiltiness to policymakers and planners to improve the EP by providing rigorous training of employees. Lastly, the investigation would further deepen unfathomable of the literature through another empirical confirmation in a developing context.

Literature review and hypotheses development

In the organizational context, training is the most significant factor of organizations' betterment (Cloutier et al., 2015). According to Abraham et al. (2021), emotional exhaustion significantly predicts job satisfaction. Holton et al. (2000) claim a positive and significant role of trainee's feedback, supervisor and co-workers, and job motivation. Mainly, feedback concerning the newly learned knowledge and skills strongly upsurges the

likelihood (Reber & Wallin, 1984). The feedback provides a sign of whether the recipient comprehends the given feedback (Sadler, 2010). In McCarthy and Garavan (2006) perception, feedback is an indispensable constituent of learning and performance throughout the upgrading developments. Whelan et al. (2010), Van der Rijt et al. (2012) observe the growing interest in feedback within organizations is enormously recognized due to its organizational success. Feedback is regarded as an effective tool to foster learning and development of employees that ultimately improve the EP (Ericsson, 2009; Salas et al., 2010; Linderbaum & Levy, 2010). In the insight of Mancini (2018), peer job satisfaction is sturdily dependent on organizational culture, role clarity and psychological empowerment. Similarly, Clossey et al. (2018) claim a predictive effect of peer support (PS) on job satisfaction. In Pakistan, Soomro et al. (2021) find a positive stimulus of organizational innovation and learning on performance. Chiaburu and Tekleab (2005) support the PS as a meaningful element for training transfer. In the entrepreneurship domain, strategic entrepreneurship confirms to be the significant predictor of the firms' financial and non-financial performance (Soomro & Shah, 2020; Shah & Soomro, 2021). Chen et al. (2007) realize the importance of environmental factors through practical training. Furthermore, an optimized role of the trainee's use of learning towards the job. Some scholars believe that as the employee gains knowledge from training and puts on it in associated job performance, positive organizational change occurs (Yamhill & McLean, 2001; Chen et al., 2007). Clarke (2002), Burke and Hutchins (2007) supports the OTU in enhancing performance. According to Bhatti et al. (2021a, b & c), motivation to learn, training content, learning styles, trainer, cognitive ability, performance goals are the significant predictors of EP. Entrepreneurial orientation has a non-significant effect on EP (Soomro & Shah, 2019). A study by Iqbal and Dastgeer (2017) highlights a mediating role of motivation to transfer in building the association between LR, self-efficacy and transfer of training. In the same domain, the outcomes of the Bhatti et al. (2013) study demonstrate a substantial influence of learner readiness on transfer motivation.

Consequently, the prior studies confirm the significant effect of feedback, LR and OTU on EP in the different contexts (Velada et al., 2007; Sadler, 2010; Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009; Mancini, 2018). Nevertheless, in Pakistani nursing setting, it needs consideration to confirm such effects (Atwater et al., 2007). Based on the insufficiency of the confirmation, we anticipated Figure 1 to endorse among the nurses of Balochistan, Pakistan.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the study

Feedback and EP

Feedback has an excellent contribution to the performance of the firms. It provides an indication from management about how well individuals perform their job (Holton et al., 2000). It is a significant factor in enhancing the prospect of its transfer to the work framework through transforming knowledge and skills (Reber & Wallin, 1984). According to Holton et al. (2000, p.346), performance works as the indicator of "formal and informal indicators from an organization about an individual's job performance". There is the prominence of feedback in the development of knowledge and skills, which ultimately make productive organizations (Ericsson, 2009; Salas et al., 2010). Similarly, a recipient's perception of the feedback regulates professional development. Once the recipient is displeased with the feedback or reflects the feedback erroneous, the recipient would probably disregard the feedback (Levy & Williams, 2004). However, some scholars looking feedback as a crucial element of learning, performance and process enlargement (McCarthy & Garavan, 2006; Atwater et al., 2007).

Consequently, the rising attention in the significance of feedback within organizations is extensively familiar because talented employees are the greatest precious asset and the key to the success of organizations (Whelan et al., 2010; Van der Rijt et al., 2012). However, reward and feedback are the most meaningful features of retorting to nursing staff work performance in the nursing element. Feedback offers nurses a sagacity of how

glowing they are undertaking their work. Henceforth, it needs more concentration and confirmation in the nursing context. Thus:

H1. Feedback positively and significantly associated with EP.

LR and EP

Trainees should have capability to retain information implanted throughout the training platform for facilitating the transfer practice. Alike, cognitive ability, LR is an extent to which trainees retain the contented after the completion of training. According to Baldwin and Ford (1988), LR consequences are unswervingly correlated with oversimplification and upkeep of training impacts on the job. Besides, trained abilities to be shifted, first they should be educated and retained. Velada et al. (2007) suggests performance self-efficacy, LR, transfer design are meaningfully linked with EP. In the perception of Fisher and Baird (2005), the integration of web-based learning has a significant positive effect on student retention in online courses. As a result, the related literature clearly shows the positive link between LR and EP (Velada et al., 2007; Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009; Clossey et al., 2018; Abraham et al., 2021). Still, in the Pakistani nurses needs more concentration. Henceforth:

H2. LR positively and significantly associated with EP.

OTU and EP

Every organization aims to achieve corporate profit and improvement in individuals' performance (Yamhill & McLean, 2001; Chen et al., 2007). A mechanism that motivates and creates the employee to transfer knowledge into the workplace is critical (Hawley & Barnard, 2005). Trainees believe that training brings several OTU the skills and knowledge. If there is limited/ insufficient training leads to resisting the OTU a new learning in their work environment (Lim & Morris, 2006). According to Clarke (2002), inadequate opportunities to implement skills on the work are the highest obstacle to successful training transfer. In the perception of Clarke (2002), Burke and Hutchins (2007), a nonexistence of opportunities result in low performance and is a blockade to actual transfer. Similarly, Lim and Johnson (2002) demonstrate that the delivery of opportunities is also an arrangement of support. Salas et al. (2010) suggest that in training to transfer efficaciously, trainees require the capitals and opportunities to put on their new skills and capabilities at the workstation. Consequently, the opportunity to use has a significant role in enhancing the EP in various contexts (Hawley & Barnard, 2005; Salas et al., 2010; Mancini, 2018). However, in the nursing context, it is in a nascent stage. Therefore:

H3. OTU positively and significantly associated with EP.

Methods

Research approach

We applied a positivism approach due to its best routine in predicting human attitudes and behaviours. It has the protagonist role in assessing EP (Gilbert, 2001). The method utilizes quantitative (numerical data), which genuinely reflect the social realities and human activities (Hussey & Hussey, 1997). Besides, the statistical analysis in such a model provides a reliable, valid and accurate picture of society (Hussey & Hussey, 1997; Gilbert, 2001). In the social science, business, management and psychology research, it is apparently due to the usage of a Likert scale, which offers a wide assortment of conceivable responses by respondents through a questionnaire (close-ended) (Oppenheim, 1992). Furthermore, several studies employed the same techniques in predicting the EP quantitatively in the different predictors and contexts (Thomas et al., 2002; Bhatti et al., 2021a, b and c).

Respondents, data collection modes and sample size

We targeted trained nurses of Balochistan, Pakistan, as the study respondents. The trained nurses are the nurses who have gotten substantial nursing training (Armstrong-Stassen et al., 2014) and utilizing their skills and are up-to-date with new ways of serving and treating the patients (Price & Reichert, 2017). Well-trained nurses possess an advanced ability in accomplishing performance goals. The technique consents employees to finish their duty with the great aptitude. The total population of nurses is 1250. 29 (nurses in District Head Quarter Hospitals); 554 (Basic Health Units), 11 (Civil Hospitals), 555 (Dispensaries), 76 (Rural Health Centers), 89 (Maternity Child Health Centers), 23 (TB Clinic), and 22 are working in Mobile Dispensaries of Balochistan's public health sector. We utilized 306 valid samples keeping in view the suggested Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table. Henceforth, we applied a random sampling for data collection. A survey package comprises study polls, a letter from the supervisor, a covering letter having the target of the review and signs for how to fill the study instrument. Before giving the surveys to the respondents, the researchers looked for well-known members for participating of their own will. Initially, 450 questionnaires were distributed personally. In return, we get a response rate of 68%.

Measures

We take all the items of the relevant elements from the previous studies. Due to the quantitative nature of the items, we used a five-point Likert scale with all the items (strongly agree=1 to strongly disagree=5).

Feedback-This factor highlights performance feedback. We applied three items of Holton et al. (2000) for measuring the feedback. These items are already used by Velada et al. (2007).

Learning retention (LR) - The LR highlights a cognitive ability to which trainee retains after the completion of training. LT is evaluated on three items. These items are borrowed from Velada et al. (2007).

Opportunity to use(OTU) - PTS underlines the opportunities after availing of the different training modes. We measured these factors using four items. These items are adopted from the study of Holton et al. (2000).

Employee performance (EP) - The EP shows the performance of employees after getting the specific training. EP is evaluated on six items adapted from the study of Xiao (1996).

Data analysis and results

Respondents' demography

In total, 306 nurses participated in the study, with a majority (64.70% or n=198) were in between 21-30 years of age. We found only 0.65% (n=02) above 51 years of age (Table 1). With regard to education level, 60.79 (n=186) nurses had intermediate degrees. 9.15% (n=28) were graduate degrees. The remaining (8.49%/n=26) were with other degrees, including matric and diplomas (Table 1). Concerning their service length, 47.06 % (n=144) nurses had health service experience, i.e. 6-10 years. Nevertheless, 43.79% (n=134) nurses were possessed 1-5 service period. Lastly, we found only 0.65 % (n=02) nurses with more than 21 years' service experience (Table 1).

Table 1. Respondents' demography

	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age (years)	< 21	21	6.87
	21-30	198	64.70
	31-40	73	23.86
	41-50	12	3.92
	51 and above	02	0.65
	Total	306	100.0
Education level	Matric	66	21.57
	Intermediate	186	60.79
	Graduate	28	9.15
	Others	26	8.49
	Total	306	100.0
Length of service (years)	1-5	134	43.79
	6-10	144	47.06
	11-15	22	7.19
	16-20	04	1.31
	21 and above	02	0.65
	Total	306	100.0

Descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients

We observed the descriptive statistics for gauging the weights of frequency. Concerning mean scores, we found maximum scores (3.552) for the opportunity to use construct. However, the feedback construct has appeared with 3.076 mean scores (Table 2). Similarly, maximum values of standard deviation (1.965) were observed for LR. Employee performance was seen with minimum scores of standard deviation as 1.020 (Table 2). Moreover, the correlational analysis underlined the health strength of Correlation among all the independent and dependent variables with Correlation at significant at the 0.01 level (**). Henceforth, the study also ensured the non-existence of multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2018) among the constructs (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4
Feedback	3.076	1.232	---			
Learning retention	3.009	1.965	0.337**	---		
Opportunity to use	3.552	1.654	0.466**	0.378**	---	
Employee performance	3.133	1.020	0.343**	0.381**	0.356**	---

Note: ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Measurement model

To gauge the reliability among the items, we conducted the factor loadings. All the scale items have appeared with > 0.70 loadings cores in the analysis (Table 3). These scores are considered to be excellent (> 0.70) (Hair et al., 2018). Besides, other indicators of the measurement model, i.e., CR and AVE for ensuring a robust correlation and identity of the items with their respective factors (CR= > 0.70 ; AVE= >0.50) (Hair et al., 2018) (Table 3). Lastly, the internal consistency among the items has been noticed as exceptional (>0.60) (Hair et al., 2018) for all constructs (feedback=0.869; LR=0.856; OTU=0.871; and EP=0.905) (Table 3).

Table 3. Measurement model

Construct	Item code	Factor loadings	CR	AVE	α
Feedback	fb1	0.890	0.883	0.798	0.869
	fb2	0.878			
	fb3	0.869			
Learning retention (LR)	lr1	0.876	0.899	0.828	0.856
	lr3	0.853			
	lr2	0.833			
Opportunity to use (OTU)	otu1	0.879	0.874	0.757	0.871
	otu2	0.858			
	otu3	0.842			
	otu4	0.807			
Employee performance (EP)	ep1	0.879	0.907	0.846	0.905
	ep2	0.858			
	ep3	0.836			
	ep6	0.803			
	ep5	0.795			
	ep4	0.769			

Notes: AVE = summation of the square of the factor loadings
CR = square of the summation of the factor loadings, α = Cronbach's alpha

Structural model

Earlier assessing the hypotheses paths, we ensured the model's fitness for robustness and the strength of further statistical tests. We found χ^2 /CMIN as 2.4084 (non-significant values or $p > 0.005$), which provided the initial insurance about basic fitness (Hair et al., 2018). Besides, other model fitness indicators (AGFI=0.911; GFI=0.929; CFI=0.948; NFI=0.939 and RMSEA=0.034) were also found within the adequate scores (Hair et al., 2018) (Table 4).

Table 4. Model fitness

Model fit indicators	CMIN/df	AGFI	GFI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA
	2.4084	0.911	0.929	0.948	0.939	0.034

Note: CMIN= χ^2 /Chi-square/df; df= degree of freedom; AGFI=adjusted goodness of fit index; GFI=goodness of fit index; CFI= comparative fit index; NFI= normed fit index; RMSEA=root mean square error of approximation

We used SEM to assess the proposed relationships. We recorded standard error (SE), critical ratio (CR) and the level of significance at $< 0.01^{***}$ as suggested by (Hair et al., 2018) for evaluating the hypotheses. The SEM analysis for H1 suggests a robust influence of feedback on EP (SE=0.032; CR=4.738 *** ; $p < 0.01$) (Figure 2 & Table 5). These values ensure the acceptance of H1. Likewise, the analysis claims a predictive effect of LR on EP (SE=0.049; CR=6.008 *** ; $p < 0.01$). Therefore, H2 is supported. In the last, the SEM outcomes also support the H3 by showing a positive significant influence of OTU on EP (SE=0.043; CR=5.889 *** ; $p < 0.01$) (Figure 2 & Table 5). In a simple sense, all the hypotheses are accepted.

Figure 2. Structural equation model

Note: LR=learning retention; OTU= opportunity to use; EP=employee performance

Table 5. SEM outcomes

Independent variables	Path	Dependent variable	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Decision
H1 Feedback	→	Employee performance	0.113	0.032	4.783	***	Accepted
H2 Learning retention	→	Employee performance	0.312	0.049	6.008	***	Accepted
H3 Opportunity to use	→	Employee performance	0.286	0.043	5.889	***	Accepted

Note: SE, standard error; CR, critical ratio; p***, significance level < 0.01

Discussion and conclusion

The objective of the investigation was to assess the influence of training and development on EP. We selected the public sector organizations of Balochistan and collected the data from the trained nurses. The study applied a quantitative method and collected cross-sectional data. The study's findings confirmed a positive significant influence of feedback on EP (H1 accepted). Such results are in line with several researchers like Whelan et al. (2010), Van der Rijt et al. (2012), who confirmed the same outcomes in the various contexts. In the light of the present results, it may reflect that the nurses of Balochistan think about the post-training conversations and their performance improvement. They feel that the application of training can be better by getting feedback. It is a strong belief of nurses that they can improve job performance through individuals' feedback. Further, the findings confirmed a predictive power of LR on EP (H2 supported). These results are also supported by various scholars (Velada et al., 2007; Clossey et al., 2018; Abraham et al., 2021). The positive findings may occur as the nurses still reminisce the core areas and topics they have learned during the training course. They believe that many things they learnt quickly and smoothly. With regard to the final hypothesis, the study also confirmed the significant effect of OTU on EP, which supported the H3. Likewise, such association/effects are accorded with many studies in the literature, i.e., Yamnill and McLean (2001), Chen et al. (2007), Mancini (2018), who found a positive predictive power of OTU on EP. These effects highlight that the nurses would be able to avail of OTU by using the training on the job. Their knowledge and information would help describe the procedures after the training. They have the confidence that they will perform well and improve their performance through the skills

they have developed through training. They also have some concerns about the limited budget in acquiring the training. They have needed sufficient resources for utilization after the learning and training.

In conclusion, the investigation's overall outcomes underlined a significant and positive influence of training and development like feedback, LR and OTU on EP among the nurses of Balochistan, Pakistan. The results would support employees in working hard and improve the quality of work in the organizations. Possibly, it may boost the confidence of employees by enhancing a few mistakes that they may commit during their careers. The nurses may further improve skills and learning by acquiring practical training. They may take advantage of opportunities to practice newly acquired skills.

The study has some limitations. The study did not take support of any concerned theory in the development of conceptualization or hypotheses. The sampling and respondents are restricted only to Balochistan. We applied a quantitative method with a single source of data collection. In future, longitudinal studies should be considered. The context of the study should extend to the overall Pakistan level. Mixed methods and qualitative studies also are conducted accordingly.

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